

Design and Evaluation of a Simulation Framework for FMCW Radar Sensors Deployed on UAV Platforms

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Abstract—This paper presents a simulation framework for FMCW radar sensors deployed on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) platforms, with a focus on airborne sensing performance. The framework models waveform generation, signal acquisition, phased array beamforming, and MIMO techniques to enhance spatial resolution. A structured point format is introduced to represent individual targets in noisy environments, enabling efficient environmental mapping and target identification. A demo software implementation demonstrates a sensor mounted on a UAV platform that scans its surroundings and delivers spatial data for exploration. The study further evaluates system setups and hardware configurations, analyzing their impact on radar functionality. This approach strengthens UAV environmental perception capabilities, supporting autonomous flight and integrated communication systems.

Index Terms—automotive driving system (ADS), frequency modulation continuous wave (FMCW), millimeter wave (mmWave), radar, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV).

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Automotive Driving Systems (ADS) have garnered significant attention and development. Numerous studies have been conducted, focusing on challenges and opportunities, as well as including hardware technologies and high-level systematic algorithms [1]. ADS serve as a key technology in the advancement of autonomous ground and aerial vehicles. In particular, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are increasingly integrating ADS to support critical applications, leveraging their features. UAVs enable remote monitoring and real-time surveillance of areas of interest, where direct access is not feasible [2]. Therefore, UAVs serve as platforms equipped with various sensors for collecting data, especially in dynamically variable environments, and a computing core for analyzing it. These functionalities enable precise localization, complete coverage mapping, sensing, and direct perception of the surrounding environment. Additionally, they ensure effective and safe autonomous flight operations, enabling informed decision-making through immediate responses and autonomous flight planning.

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Different sensors are utilized on the UAV boards to support environmental monitoring and detect unknown objects [3]. Among these sensors are involved cameras [4], LiDARs [5], and millimeter-wave (mmWave) radar sensors [6]. Camera sensing provides high-resolution analysis of the surrounding environment at short ranges. It operates by recognizing only color differences and is a very economical solution. However, it is susceptible to light conditions, failing to function effectively. Other solutions, such as LiDARs, could enhance the range of target estimation and accuracy at long distances. However, LiDAR use significantly increases the cost and is unable to operate in environments with heavy rainfall, snow, or fog. A key technology is mmWave radar, which can operate in any weather condition and benefits from its considerably low cost, small size, lightweight design, and low power consumption [7].

This work presents the development and evaluation of a simulation framework for mmWave Frequency-Modulated Continuous-Wave (FMCW) radar sensors mounted on UAV platforms. Implemented in a software-based environment, the framework models essential radar parameters and antenna configurations, including FMCW waveform characteristics, phased array beamforming, and MIMO techniques for improved spatial resolution. The simulation incorporates a structured point format to represent multiple detected targets, enabling detailed environmental mapping and target differentiation. A demo software deployment demonstrates the sensor scanning its surroundings from a UAV platform and extracting spatial data for exploration. Various system setups and hardware parameters are examined to assess their influence on radar performance. This approach enhances UAV sensing capabilities and supports future advancements in autonomous flight operations and integrated communication systems.

II. FMCW RADAR: OPERATING PRINCIPLES, SYSTEM MODEL, AND SIGNAL PROCESSING

A. System and Operation of a Monostatic Radar

Fig. 1 illustrates a subtractive model system of monostatic FMCW radar operation. Particularly, a monostatic radar sys-

Fig. 1. A block diagram of monostatic FMCW radar operation.

tem accommodates both transmitting and receiving operations. The transmitter emits an electromagnetic (EM) signal with a specified power, denoted as (P_T), and directs the signal in a steered direction. During radiation, the antenna system strengthens the signal by a factor equal to the antenna gain (G_T). EM waves propagate across the wireless channel. The wireless channel can affect the signal propagation, attenuating the power signal and varying its phase. The signal losses, described by the factor L (eq. 1), increase as we move to higher operating frequencies. At the same time, ambient conditions, including atmospheric pressure, temperature, water vapor density, and oxygen content, have a significant impact on wave propagation losses [8].

In the case of a transmitted wave that hits a target in the R range, a percentage of the propagated EM energy is reflected in the direction of the sensor. The percentage of the back is closely associated with the radar cross-section value of the target, denoted by σ . This parameter exhibits the feature of the object target to absorb signal energy or scatter the signal in multiple directions. The radar cross-section value depends on the target's geometric characteristics, such as its shape, size, orientation to polarized EM waves, and material composition. Metallic and large surfaces compared to the operating wavelength λ provide greater values. Typical radar cross-section values range from 0.01 $dBsm$ for nano drones to 10 $dBsm$ for larger drones.

Continuing, on the receiver side, the sensor can collect the EM signal if the signal exceeds a noise threshold. The received signal is enhanced by an antenna gain value, G_R , resulting in the received power. For the above discussion, we provide (1).

$$P_R = \frac{P_T G_T G_R \lambda^2 \sigma}{(4\pi)^3 R^4 L} \quad (1)$$

After the power receiver, the signal processing method begins, and the following sections describe it.

B. Frequency Modulation Continuous Waveform and Signal Processing

The mmWave automotive radar typically utilizes an FMCW signal waveform. The FMCW waveform configuration is well-suited for achieving high range resolution and an enhanced signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). At the same time, it ensures low hardware complexity, being a cost-effective solution. In this configuration, the transmitter emits a sinusoidal chirp signal,

S_t , over time, t . Representing with S the ratio of bandwidth B to chirp time duration T_c , $S = \frac{B}{T_c}$, and symbolizing f_c the frequency carrier, we consider the signal instantaneous frequency as $f_T(t) = f_c + St$. Thus, Eq. (2) summarizes the generated chirp signal, with A and ϕ_x being the wave amplitude and phase, respectively.

$$S_\tau(t) = A \cos(2\pi f_c t + \pi S t^2 + \phi_x) \quad (2)$$

The receiver side of the sensor (see Fig. 1) perceives a received signal S_R delayed by a factor $\tau = \frac{2R}{c}$, depending on the target range R and c , the speed of light. Then, the receiver mixes the transmitted and received signals, producing the S_{IF} signal. By using a low-pass filter, it retains only the lower-frequency product (3).

$$S_{IF} = LPF\{S_T S_R\} = \sin(2\pi f_{IF} t + \phi_{IF}) \quad (3)$$

$$F_{IF} = F_T - F_R = S\tau = \frac{2SR}{c} \quad (4)$$

The signal (S_{IF}) frequency F_{IF} , described in (4), as the difference between the transmitted and received frequency, provides information for the possible target range. In addition, (4) specifies the discriminative ability of the radar, or in other words, the minimum distance between different targets that are detectable. If the use of bandwidth is increased, the range resolution of detected objects is improved.

Beyond the target range, it is very important that the sensing operation identifies the object's velocity. The maximum velocity that can be detected depends on the duration of the time chirp. Notably, as the chirp time is reduced, it allows for an increase in the maximum detectable speed, since $V_{max} < \frac{\lambda}{4T_c}$, where λ is the operating wavelength. However, hardware systems impose constraints on the minimum bound of chirp duration. In addition, the velocity resolution or accuracy is defined by the number of chirps N_c used in each transmission. Although increasing the number of chirps results in a longer duration of frame time ($N_c T_c$), it contributes to higher velocity resolution, as $V_{res} < \frac{\lambda}{2N_c T_c}$.

Furthermore, we should note that distinct objects with similar range positions and velocities may be distinguished, considering the provided angular resolution. The angle resolution in the azimuth or elevation planes depends on the number

Fig. 2. The FMCW chirp signal in a frequency-time diagram.

of distinct receiver elements N_R spaced at a distance d in the corresponding plane, as is illustrated in (5).

$$\theta_{res} = \frac{\lambda}{2dN_R} \quad (5)$$

III. ANTENNA ARCHITECTURES IN RADAR SYSTEMS

The hardware complexity of a radar system is closely tied to its antenna architecture and configuration. The overall architecture may increase the hardware complexity and cost. At the same time, the flexibility of antenna system configuration has a significant impact on the enhanced sensing functionalities. Phased antenna array design and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technologies are the primary principles of antenna layouts in radars. Below, we discuss these technological terms.

A. Phased Array Antennas

Phased array antennas can form and steer the main beam pattern. So, its integration allows the EM energy to be directed in the desired direction, rejecting undesired EM interferences from other sides. The antenna elements, arranged in a linear array, are equipped with scanning capability on the azimuth plane, in contrast to rectangular topologies or those with scanning capability on both the azimuth and elevation planes. Concurrently, phased array topologies offer the capability to widen the beam pattern or make more tilt, depending on the desired detection target range and characteristics. It should be noted that progress has been made in silicon technologies, and mmWave beamforming integrated circuits (ICs) have been contributing to the incorporation of phased array antennas in radar systems [9], [10].

The phased array layout consists of N_T antenna elements, each of them followed by a cascade line that includes an RF amplifier and a phase shifter, which adjust the amplitude and phase, respectively. Each combination of the power amplitude weights and the phased difference between adjacent antenna elements creates a unique radiation pattern with specific characteristics. As the total antenna system increases to improve performance on the range, it also increases complexity. So for this reason, the antenna arrays are grouped into larger arrays, as a consequence of which larger array antennas have a

Fig. 3. Phased array antenna configuration.

Fig. 4. Virtual receiver antenna array synthesis for MIMO radar.

cascade of amplifiers and phase shifters following them. Fig. 3 illustrates this approach, where N_T represents the number of cascade lines and M_i denotes the number of elements in each array.

B. Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) Radar Antenna System

In a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) radar architecture, the radar system comprises multiple transmitters and multiple receiver antennas. Fig. 4 presents an example of a MIMO radar system utilizing two transmitters (Tx1 and Tx2) with four receivers (Rx1, Rx2, Rx3, and Rx4), and compares it to a simple radar model. The simplified approach involves one transmitter (Tx1) interacting with four receivers (Rx1-Rx4). In the MIMO setup, we observe that a virtual receiver array with dimensions of the product of the number of transmitters, N_T , and receivers, N_R , is synthesized. In contrast, the receiver array in the case of one transmitter use is only dependent on the number of receiver antenna elements, N_R . In this way, and by combining the (5), we can achieve a higher angular resolution [11] and [12]. This strategy becomes more critical in larger array antennas, as it prevents each receiver antenna from using a separate processing chain to increase the angular resolution. Such an approach will undoubtedly lead to higher-complexity system designs with higher costs.

A MIMO system typically operates with time division multiplexing (TDM), thereby avoiding EM interference between wireless channels. Additionally, this means that the TDM MIMO technique divides the total time frame of emission according to the number of transmitters. This strategy affects the maximum detectable velocity, which is compensated for by synchronizing the receiving signals at the receiver side.

IV. SIGNAL PROCESSING FRAMEWORK IMPLEMENTATION

A. Signal Processing Flow Diagram

This section discusses the processes of data storing, organization, and processing, as well as the extraction of information about unknown objects detected and the management of hardware and system resources. This section can be grouped

into four main categories: a) data storage and organizing, b) signal processing methods are employed, c) identification of algorithms for detecting characteristics of unknown targets, and d) management of power and spectrum efficiency during 3D scanning environment.

1) **Storing and Organizing Data in 3D Datacubes:** As we previously discussed, each transmitter radiates N_c signal chirps. The receiver side collects each received signal and samples it, generating N_s samples. The signal data are represented in the time domain. At each time step corresponding to a chirp index, the receiver is loaded with collecting data from all virtual antenna array elements $N_T N_R$ (where N_T and N_R are the numbers of transmitters and receiver RF channels), to store and organize them into three-dimensional (3D) buffers.

2) **Digital Signal Processing:** We then applied various digital signal processing methods to reduce noise and enhance the signal. The data process is realized by each dimension, starting from N_s samples for each RF channel, and is repeated for each time frame or chirp. There, we apply FIR filters to reject unnecessary information. Resampling methods are implemented either to reduce the data volume or enhance the signal resolution. Other techniques, such as windowing and zero padding, have a practical impact on frequency domain transformation.

Signal information about the target position and velocity is encoded in signal frequency bins. Therefore, to derive information about the detected target, we apply Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to each dimension, a total of three times. In this way, even though the info is located in the frequency domain, the signal data continues to be organized into three data cubes. Additionally, the data can be formatted as range-velocity and range-angle responses, making the information clearer in a visual representation.

3) **Signal Detection Algorithms:** Furthermore, we extract the signal frequency information, expressed as spectral power, by integrating Constant False Alarm Rate (CFAR) or Capon algorithms. The CFAR algorithm estimates a noise threshold in a local region of the signal data and examines if there is a signal power peak that exceeds this threshold. In such a case, it means that a range and velocity target have been detected. On the other hand, the Capon algorithm is used to extract information for range and angle objects. The Capon algorithm is an adaptive beamforming technique that adjusts signal weights in specific directions, thereby emphasizing and focusing on angular resolution for precise detection of object angles. The generated information, concerning signal peak values, object position, and angle, will be beneficial for other tasks in automotive flight, such as object classification and tracking.

4) **Managing System Efficiency and Controlling 3D Scanning:** Additionally, a more generic description of a radar sensor includes the management of power efficiency, frequency spectrum, and time sources. Therefore, the integrated algorithm scans the 3D environment coverage and executes the primary operations outlined in the above signal processing flow diagrams in a more efficient way. Considering the extraction of information for the number of unknown objects and

Fig. 5. Signal processing flow diagram.

their characteristics, it is responsible for effectively controlling the system's sources. Table I illustrates the processing steps of a radar sensor operation in a pseudocode format.

TABLE I
MMWAVE FMCW RADAR SENSOR MANAGEMENT ALGORITHM

Algorithm: mmWave FMCW Radar Sensor Management Algorithm
Inputs: Antenna Layout Architecture, Phased Array Antenna Capabilities, TDM MIMO operation, and FMCW Waveform Settings.
Loop: While system is running
For each scanning angle in the sensor FoV:
Search for unknown objects.
If object detected:
Record angles, range, and angular data
Store detection history
For each previously detected object:
Predict object characteristics for the next time step.
If velocity has a high value:
Adjust number of chirps - for power-time efficiency
If object is far:
Adjust the power and beam pattern
Else:
Reduce the power for efficiency performance

V. EVALUATION OF SENSING SYSTEM

A. System Configuration

For the scope of FMCW implementation, we first set our radar model by specifying the aperture array antenna characteristics in the transmitter and receiver. In our system settings, we consider the radar sensor to include three separate transmitters and one receiver operating on 77 GHz frequency, forming a sparse MIMO with a co-prime configuration [13], to eliminate EM interference. Each transmitter consists of two channels of 8 antenna elements, providing a total gain of approximately 19.8 dBi. We also consider that the power transmission for each transmitter chain is limited 20 mW, to maintain low power consumption, and supported by beamforming ICs available from industry trade [14]. Concerning the receiver aperture array, it is designed to consist of 8 distinct RF chains, where each of them ends in 16 antenna elements. Thereby, the receiver antenna system attributes a 28.8 dBi gain. To note that the described antenna layout mimics the characteristics of market radar sensors, to predict the performance of these

sensors. Additionally, we did not further concentrate on the hardware digital system components, such as the amplifier, analog-to-digital converters (ADCs), and phase-locked loop (PLL) components. Such an approach would increase system complexity, which is beyond the scope of the sensor functionality in this work. For example, the non-linearities of amplifiers in combination with phase deviations caused by the PLL components and ADC quantization noise distort the signal target estimation.

Moreover, we parameterize the linear FMCW waveform settings. We initially define a signal sweep bandwidth of 300 MHz, offering a range resolution of 50 cm. The chirp duration, set to 15 μ s, enables the detection of moving targets up to 230 km/h. We also refer that each transmitter is active for a time frame equal to 3.85 ms, supporting $N_c = 256$ chirps. During simulation execution, it is worth noting that the waveform settings are varied to reduce power consumption, enhance sensing performance, and optimize frequency and time resources.

B. Simulation Results and Discussion

We investigated multiple approaches, examining different goals each time. Specifically, this work focuses on three cases that highlight sensor performance. First, we demonstrate and confirm the right functionality of the radar sensor. Secondly, we perform a parametric analysis to examine the sensor quality metrics in different cases. Ultimately, we evaluate the benefits of TDM MIMO configurations compared to a single transmitter in terms of their impact on target estimation and system requirements.

1) **Range Doppler Response:** Herein, we analyze the capability of a sensor loaded in a UAV to detect other aerial objects. In modeling the environment, we consider four randomly distributed targets in the airspace, each presenting an RCS of 10 dBsm. Each target object also represents a position in the air, while a monostatic radar employed in a UAV is located at the position (0 m, 0 m, 300 m). We also assume that object targets execute a movement with an instantaneous velocity value. These target characteristics are included in Table II.

TABLE II
TARGETS WITH POSITION, VELOCITY, AND RCS

Target	Position (m)	Velocity (m/s)	RCS (dBsm)
1	(93, -2, 300)	-14.6	10
2	(68, 38, 300)	3.4	10
3	(45, -18, 300)	-15	10
4	(70, 14, 300)	-14	10

Fig. 6 illustrates the range-velocity response. This diagram illustrates the detection of defined objects, denoted by red circles, with minor variations in speed. We also observe that target objects with a shorter distance range exhibit a higher signal peak strength and lower energy spread compared to those that are farther away.

Fig. 6. Range-Doppler map, showing the detection of four different targets.

Fig. 7. Range-Doppler map using a) low $N_c = 32$, and b) high $N_c = 256$ number of chirps.

2) **Coherent Processing Integration:** We also investigate signal processing techniques to improve target estimation. Thus, we examine the integration of coherent time, modifying and adjusting the number of signal repetitions to the target characteristics. Particularly, Fig. 7 compares the range velocity response for two sensor scanning scenarios. The first defines a repetition of chirps at $N_c = 32$, resulting in a shorter scanning time, and the second uses $N_c = 256$, resulting in a longer scanning time. We observe that for a low number of chirps, the frequency spectrum is spread across a wide range, while the noise power increases. In contrast, for a higher number of chirps, the signal power of the detected object targets is more precise and accurate, concentrating on a single point. This is explained as in an increasing number N_c , the sensor observes for a longer time duration in each scanning area. This approach facilitates the application of the FFT algorithm to signal data, considering more signal points to achieve a higher frequency spectrum resolution.

Concurrently, the requirements of the SNR metric performance for a detectable object in a specified position are reduced by a factor of $10 \log N_c$. This result is also evident in the diagram in Fig. 8, which illustrates the required transmitted power versus range for various numbers of chirps, ranging from 8 to 1024. Note that SNR is computed by considering the probability of detection over 0.9 and a false error rate equal to 10^{-6} , apart from coherent integration. Synchronously, for the SNR calculation, we did not consider the hardware constraints imposed by the ADC converters, while assuming a receiver noise figure below 7 dB and a temperature of 300 K.

Fig. 8. The diagram shows the required transmit power versus range for object detection with varying numbers of coherently integrated chirps.

Fig. 9. Range-Angle map for two cases of monostatic radar: (a) without and (b) with TDM MIMO operation.

3) **TDM MIMO Configuration**: The last case study focuses on the utilization of MIMO technology. Particularly, we compare two radar models. The first model integrates only one transmitter, whereas the second uses three transmitters with TDM MIMO operation. Thereby, the number of virtual RF channels in the MIMO case is increased, offering a more accurate angle estimation of the detected object. Fig. 9 shows the range-angle map for both discussed instances, showing the detection of one target with a formed angle with the sensor at 17° . In MIMO, the spectral signal power is concentrated at a specific angle point. In contrast to the simple case, where the transmitter's peak values are spread across multiple angle points and sidelobes are formed, resulting in a degradation of the detection process. Note that in both cases, the total active time of the transmitters is the same, so without it, there is an imbalance in power consumption, memory requirements, or signal processing chains between the two cases. However, the single transmitter offers the flexibility to remain active for a time frame longer than the transmitters in MIMO operation, in proportion to the number of transmitters. This also allows the maximum measurable velocity to be higher compared to the case with multiple transmitters in MIMO operation.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presented the deployment of a 77 GHz mmWave FMCW sensor radar on a UAV for its environment sensing. The significance of this work lies in its tutorial nature, which discusses the main technical specifications. Particularly, it focuses on signal waveform settings, as well as analyzing antenna aperture array architectures and technologies. Additionally, we demonstrated an algorithm for managing and

controlling the radar sensor functionalities, as well as a signal processing flow diagram for data analysis. Furthermore, we investigated three examples by parameterizing the FMCW settings and antenna system architecture, and we discussed and evaluated the resulting mmWave sensor performance. Finally, our future work will integrate the algorithm sensing operation with mmWave radar sensors mounted on UAV platforms and investigate its performance under real environmental conditions.

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